

ISic0064

I.Sicily inscription 0064

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Tuuli Ahlholm,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arco) · Aureliø
2. Vero · CaesareCaesari co(n)s(uli)
3. Imp(eratori)
4. T(iti) · Aeli · Hadriani
5. Antonini · Aug(usti)
6. Pii · filio
7. p(ecunia) · p(ublica) · d(ecreto) · d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491853

EDR 142423

EDCS 22100592

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7473 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650805>)

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Raepsaet-Charlier, M.-Th. 1974. A propos du récent catalogue d'inscriptions latines du musée de Palerme. *Latomus*. 33: 124-127. At 126

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 71 no.3 fig.33

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